

**EFFECT OF DRILLING AND STRENGTHENING COLUMNS ON
STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS OF TOWERS.**

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ABSTRACT. As we know, the study of the influence of some gravity on the structure of the towers and the wells to a certain extent during the lifting and lowering of the plugs through the towers during the operation of the control mechanisms of the drilling towers during the drilling work is reflected in this article. Presidential Decree No. PD-309, issued on 07.07.2022, on measures to establish an education-production cluster in the oil and gas sector, occupies an important place in the Master-Apprentice system. Our main goal is to economically use every mine, as man digs out natural resources from the depths of the generous mother earth, says our Honorable President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich. At the summary meeting of the results of oil and gas production and processing at the end of 2022: 118 fields are under control of JSC "Uzbekneftgaz" in the Republic of Uzbekistan, natural gas is being extracted from 85 of them, and geological-control exploration works are being carried out in the remaining 33 fields. In 2022, in order to increase the efficiency of the system in the production of oil and gas, effective results have been achieved on the rational use of hydrocarbon deposits, the increase in the production of natural gas and liquid hydrocarbon raw materials, he said in his speech. The share of JSC "Uzbekneftgaz" in the production of hydrocarbons in Uzbekistan is 63.0% in natural gas production, 67.0% in gas condensate production, and 13.0% in oil production.

Key words: Drilling rigs, control mechanisms in drilling work, plugs, gravity, rig construction

ВЛИЯНИЕ БУРЕНИЯ И УКРЕПЛЕНИЯ КОЛОНН НА КОНСТРУКТИВНЫЕ ЭЛЕМЕНТЫ БАШЕН.

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Аннотация. Как известно, изучение влияния силы тяжести на конструкцию башен и скважин в определенной степени при подъеме и опускании пробок через башни при работе механизмов управления буровыми башнями при бурении. Работа отражена в этой статье. Важное место в системе «мастер-ученик» занимает Указ Президента № ПП-309 от 07.07.2022 г. «О мерах по созданию учебно-производственного кластера в нефтегазовой сфере». Наша главная цель – экономно использовать каждую шахту, так как человек выкапывает природные ресурсы из недр щедрой матушки-земли, – говорит наш уважаемый Президент Шавкат Мирзиёев Мираманович. На сводном совещании подведены итоги добычи и переработки нефти и газа по итогам 2022 года: Под управлением АО «Узбекнефтегаз» в Республике Узбекистан находится 118 месторождений, из них 85 ведется добыча природного газа, геолого-контрольная. На остальных 33 месторождениях ведутся геологоразведочные работы. В 2022 году в целях повышения эффективности системы добычи нефти и газа достигнуты эффективные результаты по рациональному использованию месторождений

углеводородов, увеличению добычи природного газа и жидкого углеводородного сырья, сказал он в его речь. Доля АО «Узбекнефтегаз» в добыче углеводородов в Узбекистане составляет 63,0% по добыче природного газа, 67,0% по добыче газового конденсата, 13,0% по добыче нефти.

Ключевые слова. Буровые установки, механизмы управления при буровых работах, пробки, гравитация, буровая конструкция

БУРҒУЛАШ ВА МУСТАҲКАМЛАШ КОЛОННАЛАРНИ ТУШИРИБ КЎТАРИШДА МИНОРАЛАРНИ КОНСТРУКТИВ ЭЛЕМЕНТЛАРИГА ТАЪСИРИ.

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АННОТАЦИЯ. Бизга маълумки бурғуловчи миноралар бурғулаш ишида бошқарувчи механизмларини ҳаракатга келтиришда миноралар орқали свечалар кўтарилиб ўрнатилиши ёки туширилишида бир қанча оғирлик кучи таъсирида миноралар конструкциясига ҳамда қудуқларни маълум даражада таъсирини ўрганиш ушбу мақолада акс эттирилган. Нефт ва газ соҳасида таълим-ишлаб чиқариш кластерини ташкил этиш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисидаги ПҚ-309 сон, 07.07.2022 йилда чиқарилган Президент қарори Устоз-шогирд тизимида муҳим ўрин эгалламоқда. Инсон саховатли она ер қаъридан табиий бойликларни қазиб олар экан, ҳар бир кондан тежамкорона фойдаланиш асосий мақсадимиздир дейди Ҳурматли Президентимиз Шавкат Мирзиёев Миромонович. 2022 йил якунидаги нефть ва газ қазиб чиқариш ҳамда қайта ишлаш бўйича натижалар

сарҳисоби йиғилишида: Ўзбекистон Республикасида «Ўзбекнефтверг» АЖ таркибига 118 та кон назоратга олинган бўлиб, 85 тасидан табиий газ қазилмоқда, қолган 33 та конда эса геология-назорат қидирув ишлари олиб борилмоқда. 2022 йилда тизимнинг нефт ва газ ишлаб чиқаришдаги фойдали иш коэффициентлари юқори бўлиши учун углеводород конларидан оқилона фойдаланиш, табиий газ ва суюқ углеводород хом ашёси қазиб чиқаришни ошириш бўйича самарали натижаларга эришилди дейилади ўз нутқида. «Ўзбекнефтверг» АЖнинг Ўзбекистонда углеводородларни қазиб чиқаришдаги улуши табиий газ қазиб чиқариш бўйича 63,0 фоиз, газ конденсати қазиб чиқариш бўйича 67,0 фоиз, нефть қазиб чиқариш бўйича 13,0 фоизни ташкил этади.

Kalit so'zlar. Бурғуловчи миноралар, бурғулаш ишида бошқарувчи механизмлар, свечалар, оғирлик кучи, миноралар конструкцияси

INTRODUCTION. On November 20, Shavkat Mirziyoyev defined tasks for the development of the oil and gas industry, i.e. 30 investment projects with a total value of 36.5 billion dollars in geological exploration, hydrocarbon extraction and deep processing until 2030 for the further development of the oil and gas industry. implementation is defined. The derrick is the key to the start-up of the drilling rigs. A derrick is basically a lifting structure that is installed on top of a wellbore. Drilling tools, downhole (zaboy) engines are used to lower and raise the well wall reinforcement pipes. The tower we are experimenting with is of metal construction. Drilling works carried out in the well No. 323 in the "Zevarda" gas condensate field under the control of the Mubarak oil and gas production department of Kashkadarya region were also successfully completed, and a filter between 2800-2667 m² was dropped. After the development of the well, 100,000 cubic meters of industrial-scale natural gas and 1 ton of gas condensate were produced per day. For information: "Zevarda" mine is located in Mirishkor district of Kashkadarya region and has been used since 1979. A communication tower and an 800-meter-long optical fiber communication cable were laid between the "Zevarda" complex gas preparation device and the "Zevarda"

compression compressor station. Also, a communication cabinet, "AVT-850AVR", "Ethernet" switching devices and network points were installed in the "Mechanical workshop" building of the "Zevarda" mine. A communication cabinet, "AVT-850AVR", "Ethernet" switching devices were installed for the communication tower of the "Zevarda" compression compressor station facility, and a 100-meter long "UTP" network cable was laid. This compression compressor station and the "Pamuq" complex gas preparation device, the "Power Beam 5ac-620" radio bridge device to the station in the direction of "Sardob", and the "Lite Beam 5AC Gen2" radio bridge device from the station to the "Zevarda worker's town" direction were installed and put into operation.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. As we know, the height of the drilling tower will be from 9 to 58 meters, depending on the depth of the well specified in the project. The tower we are considering is 41 meters. This tower was moved from one place to another with the help of tractors, and separated into separate sections and reassembled at a new place.

Schematic diagram of a 4-legged tower in a derrick

Base view of tower 1, base of tower 2, footing of tower 3, ladder, 4-steel pipe farm, 5-place for worker to work on top, 6-installation place for crown block, 7-top part of tower, 8-tubes in cradle (plugs), 9-crown block area part, 10-cradle, 11-pipe holder (pallets) view

The drilling tower performs the following tasks:

Drill string maintenance in a mobile system during drop-down drilling;

Shut-off operations with casing and drill pipes;

Installation of the Tall system in motion and means of mechanization of waiting and dismounting of propulsion operations, including platforms of mounted work equipment, ASP and KMSP mechanisms;

The structure of the location of the drilling tower must meet the following basic requirements:

1. the construction and dimensions of the towers fully comply with the technical safety regulations;

2. the height of the towers corresponds to the depth of the well;

3. to have the ability to carry all loads when performing drilling and special works (strengthening of pipes, lifting, destruction works);

4. have the necessary dimensions for the correct placement of drilling mechanisms;

5. protection of workers and mechanisms from weather events;

6. to have structures that are convenient for assembling, disassembling, and moving towers from one place to another.

During the operation of the drilling tower, the following points are taken into account.

1) the tower is assembled correctly;

2) strength of bolts and supports;

3) the strength of the girder of the crane block and the crane blocks;

4) non-deformation of the tower leg and details;

- 5) straightness of the leg of the tower and the distance between the junctions;
- 6) condition of welds;
- 7) violation of the balance (geometry) of the tower;
- 8) technical condition of tower foundations;
- 9) the distance between the center and diagonal legs of the tower;
- 10) location and stability of the area and stairs;
- 11) the technical condition of the towbars must be at the required level.

The impact of the drilling tower on the columns in well No. 323 of the Zevarda mine, located in the Mubarak district of Kashkadarya region, was studied, and the weight calculation of the vertically upright tower was carried out.

In the process of constructing wells, the structure of the well was studied as follows when choosing drilling towers. The 377 mm conductor was lowered to a depth of 300 meters, and the 168 mm drilling assembly was lowered to a depth of 1900 meters. Drilling is done with 168 mm drill pipe, to which 203 mm weighted drill pipe is attached, the weighted drill pipe length (obq) is 75 meters. If we calculate the weight of the drilling rig:

First of all, in determining the maximum vertical weight loads of the working derrick, we determined the weight of the conductor as follows:

When calculating the weight of a vertical tower, it is important to choose a drilling tower during the construction of wells. Therefore, the structure of the well includes the following: a 377 mm conductor is lowered to 300 m, a 168 mm drilling joint is lowered to a depth of 1900 meters, and it is drilled with 168 mm drill pipes, as a result, a 203 mm weighted drill

pipe is attached to it. The length of the weighted drill pipe (obq) is 75 meters. First, when calculating the weight of the tower, we determine the maximum vertical weight loads that the derrick can carry, and then we determine the weight of the conductor as follows:

$$Y_0 = q_1 H + q_m H / L = 1.08 * 300 + 0.31 * 300 / 10 = 333 \text{ kN}$$

In this formula $q_1 = 1.08 \text{ kN}$ - Weight of 1 meter smooth pipe, kN (kg)

$q_m = 0.31 \text{ kN}$ - one clutch or lock weight, kN (kg);

$L = 10$ meter. This indicates the average pipe length (m).

RESULTS. Similarly, to find the spacing of the 168 mm bore pipe, we take the value from [Elyashevsky] and put it into the formula:

$q_m = 0.39 \text{ kN}$ and $q_m = 0.093 \text{ kN}$ if we check it,

$Y_0 = q_1 H + q_m H / L = 0.39 * 1900 + 0.093 * 1900 / 10 + 759$ we got.

Here, the number of pipes in the 1900/10 intermediate joints, the weight of the drilling equipment

$$G = q_1 (H - L_{w.a.p}) + L_{w.a.p} * q_{w.a.p}$$

Here q_1 - Weight of 1 meter long 168mm drill pipe, kN (kg); $L_{w.a.p}$ - 203 mm of weighted drill pipe, 1 m length weight, kN(kg), $q_c = 0.5 \text{ kN}$; $q_{w.a.p} = 2 \text{ kN}$.

If we put the determined values in the above formula, $G = q_1 (H - L_{w.a.p}) + L_{w.a.p} * q_{w.a.p} = 0.5(1900-75) + 752 * 2 = 1062.5 \text{ kN}$

DISCUSSION. The weight of the drill pipe assemblies and equipment was taken into account in the calculations. We find the weight of hook, tally block, elevator, and crane block as follows: $q_{il} = 15.7 \text{ kN}$, $q_{tb} = 33 \text{ kN}$; $q_c = 1.5 \text{ kN}$; $q_{kb} = 24.2 \text{ kN}$

Then we $G_1 = q_{il} + q_{tb} + q_c + q_{kb}$ We calculated by putting the determined value in this formula: $G_1 = q_{il} + q_{tb} + q_c + q_{kb} = 15.7 + 33 + 1.5 + 24.2 = 74.4 \text{ kN}$

If we determine the tensile strength for fixed and movable ropes:

$P = \frac{G}{n}$, here n – the number of working rollers of the tally block, if we enter

accuracy in the formula, $P = \frac{G}{n} = \frac{1062.5}{4} = 266 \text{ kN}$

IN CONCLUSION, it should be said that in drilling pipe placement, the placement of weighted drill pipe from the well;

The rig is installed on top of the well to raise and lower the drilling equipment (casing pipes, well motors, etc.). It is a special platform for the interaction and maintenance of the ladder and crown block.

The total maximum weight of the derrick was found as follows:

We find the total weight of the rig as follows:

$$Q_{\max} = G + G_1 + P + P_{ok}$$

In this expression $P_{e.p}$ – excess power, kN; $P_{e.p}$ – 500 from 600kN we got up to.

$$Q_{\max} = G + G_1 + P + P_{e.p} = 1062,5 + 74,4 + 266 + 500 = 1902,9 \text{ kN} = 1,903 \text{ MN}$$

approximately this value was equal to 2 MN.

In order to prevent the complications of accidents with reinforcing columns, it is necessary to carry out the necessary work.

First, before lowering the reinforcing columns, it is necessary to prepare the well column (check the parameters of the expansion and drilling solutions).

Second, inspection of hoists and elevators before inspection of reinforcing columns.

Thirdly, in the process of lowering the column, check the exit of the drilling fluids from the well and fill the column in time.

Fourth, the driller, driller or responsible person must constantly monitor the hardening of the pipe threads.

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